

COVID^X

DATA vs COVID-19 GAME ON

DEFEATING COVID-19 WITH DATA SOLUTIONS

OPEN CALL

COVID-19 Data Technology
Solutions, ready-to-market [TRL 7+]
with CE marking [or in process]

APPLY NOW

DEADLINE

22 July 2021, 17:00 CEST

MORE INFO

www.covid-x.eu

FUNDING

100 K€

X1 EU TECH COMPANY

*VALIDATION AT COVID-X
CLINICAL SITES

150 K€

X1 EU TECH COMPANY

+

X1 EU HEALTHCARE
PROVIDER

● SINGLE
— PLAYER

● MULTI
— PLAYER

ACCELERATION
PROGRAM

DATA
SANDBOX

TECHNICAL
SUPPORT

ETHICAL
VALIDATION

BUSINESS
COACHING

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#GameON

COVID-X has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101016065. The content of this document does not represent the opinion of the European Union, and the European Union is not responsible for any use that might be made of such content.